

A Study on the Role and Promotion of Geriatrics Industry by the English Dailies

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Abstract—The geriatrics industry, encompassing medical care and services for the elderly, is of paramount importance in an increasingly aging world. As the elderly population grows, so too does the demand for specialized healthcare, social services, and products tailored to their needs. The media plays a pivotal role in shaping public perception, influencing policy, and promoting various industries, including geriatrics not only that English-language daily newspapers play a significant role in shaping public opinion, influencing healthcare policies and portrayal and promotion of the geriatrics industry.

I. INTRODUCTION

I.I. GERIATRICS

Geriatrics is that focuses on health care of elderly people. By preventing and treating illnesses and problems in older individuals, it seeks to enhance health.

I.II. HEALTH COMMUNICATION

Health Communication is the study of communicating promotional health information, such as in health education, public health campaigns and between doctors and patients.

The Purpose of disseminating health information is to influence personal health choices by improving health literacy, because effective health communication must be adapted among the audience and the situation. The goal of health communication research is to improve communication tactics for informing the public about methods to improve their health or prevent certain health concerns.

I.III. PRINT MEDIA

The mass media plays an important role in our day to day life. Collectively media comprises television, newspaper, radio and internet which reach the mass of the people. It plays the role of informing, educating the masses. Also media provide both positive and negative portrayals of people that allow individuals to develop ideas and characterize people based on certain attributes like age, race, and gender. These days, its function goes beyond simply reporting news; it also evaluates and comments on the facts, so influencing people's opinions.

The media has been setting for the nation its social, political, economic and even cultural agenda and hence media can be used powerfully in spreading awareness on human health and elderly people's health.

I.IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Geriatrics, the medical care of older adults, is a complex and growing field. It encompasses the prevention and treatment of diseases and disabilities in this population Vaishya, R. (2019). This care is particularly important given the vulnerability of geriatric patients to medication-related risks, such as adverse outcomes and drug toxicity Omar Al, K., & Syed Iqbal, M. (2022). According to Azimi, I. et al. (2017), Technological advancements have increased life expectancy, leading to an increased demand for elderly care services. The Internet of Things (IoT) has been introduced to improve remote elderly monitoring. However, there is a lack of user-centered studies for elderly care needs. This paper explores IoT-enabled systems for elderly monitoring, categorizing existing approaches and introducing a hierarchical model for elderly-centered monitoring. The study aims to evaluate objectives and trends in IoT-based elderly monitoring systems to improve their quality of life. As per Ni Scanaill, C. et al. (2006), Technological advancements have led to the development of tele monitoring systems for chronic conditions prevention, early diagnosis, and management. These systems can reduce hospital admissions, improve clinical visits, and reduce hospital stays for elderly individuals. Monitoring mobility can help assess health status, as it is a good indicator of health status. Health smart homes, wearables, and combination systems are being explored for remote

monitoring. As per WHO (2018) The demographic shift, with 80% of older people in low- and middle-income countries by 2050, is causing major challenges for health and social systems, with the proportion of the world's over-60-year-old population nearly doubling between 2015 and 2050. According to Tanabe, S. et al. (2019), The Robotic Smart Home (RSH) project aims to create a comfortable, safe home environment for the elderly and disabled individuals. The project combines robots and architectural design to create an optimal living space. The RSH includes three robotics and assistive systems: mobility and transfer assist, operational assist, and information assist. The system accommodates users based on their disability severity, and includes a home automation and monitoring system connected to the Internet of Things. There are now two RSH centres available for efficient facility implementation.

II. RESEARCH DESIGN

The structure of the methodology is an important factor in itself. Choosing the suitable methods to formulate a research design is vital to the research process. The research design sets the framework for the research to be taken up and allows the research to be initiated. It serves as the answer to how the research will be taken up, how data will be collected and analyzed, and through which manner it will be done so.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study will use a mixed methodology of both quantitative and qualitative research methods. The following methods will be employed:

- Content Analysis

III.I. TOOLS OF DATA COLLECTION

The tools of data collection refer to different media from which we get the data of our study. The collected data will be subjected to various methods of analysis to meet the objectives. The data are collected from the news reports and news analysis in which geriatric health care is covered from top 2 English daily Newspapers- 'The New Indian Express' and 'Time of India'.

III.II. SAMPLING

Sampling is the process of selection of observations to acquire some knowledge of statistical population. The top two English dailies in India have been analyzed for this study: 'The New Indian Express' and The Times of India. A period of one month, from January 01, 2024 to January 31, 2024 has been set for this study. This time frame has been selected considering that it covers geriatric health care news during this period. A purposive sampling method was taken up to procure all geriatric health care -related news that fall on the front page, city pages and supplementary of the two newspapers, bringing a total of 43 articles.

III.III. ANALYSIS

Data collected through content analysis of the geriatric healthcare articles featured in the newspapers The New Indian Express and The Times of India are presented and analyzed in this chapter. The analysis compares the newspapers' involvement in Health communication during a one month period covering the geriatric healthcare. The statistical technique aspect of the analysis is done.

III.III. I. KIND OF GERIATRIC HEALTHCARE NEWS REPORTED

All the new items carrying news about geriatric health care are studied to know the kind of news that were happened and reported by media in the study period. And they were found to be Health tips, Achievement / travel, Government policy / insurance, Medicare, Therapy, Safety, Risk, Homecare and General.

Kind of news reported	The New Indian Express	Times of India	Total
Health tips	7	6	13
Achievement / travel	1	2	3
Government policy / insurance	2	4	6
Medicare	Nil	1	1
Therapy	2	4	6
Safety	4	Nil	4
Risk	Nil	1	1
Homecare	5	5	10
General	7	2	6

Table 1. Kind of geriatric healthcare news reported

III.III. II. CATEGORIZATION OF NEWS ITEMS

All the news items covering geriatric health care were generally categorized into Policy/politics, Workforce, Industrial, Education, Legal/Ethical, Gender, Age, Ethnicity, Socio/Economic, Geographic/Demographic, Promotion, Prevention, Events and Treatment, Rehabilitation, Facilities, Technology and Research category.

The news and article that contains straight information on the events happenings is counted under the Geographic/Demographic, Promotion, Prevention, Events category and the news that contains the government policy and insurance for elder people is counted under the Policy/politics category and health tips that covered under the Gender, Age, Ethnicity, Socio/Economic category.

Category combination	Proportion all items		The New Indian Express		Times of India	
	%	n	%	n	%	n
• Policy/politics	14	2	7	2	0	0
• Workforce,Industrial, Education,Legal/Ethical	13	7	11	3	16	4
• Gender,Age,Ethnicity,Socio/Economic	9	5	7	2	12	3
• Geographic/Demographic, Promotion, Prevention,events	42	22	43	12	40	10
• Treatment,Rehabilitation, Facilities,Technology and Research	32	17	32	9	32	8
Total	100	53	47	28	53	25

Table 2. Categorization of news items

It was found that of all news and article items in ‘The New Indian Express’ , 7% are the politics and policy, 11% are Workforce, Industrial, Education, Legal/Ethical, 7% Gender, Age, Ethnicity, Socio/Economic, 43% Geographic/Demographic, Promotion, Prevention, Events and 32% Treatment, Rehabilitation, Facilities, Technology and Research. Similarly 0% are the politics and policy, 16% are Workforce, Industrial, Education, Legal/Ethical, 12% Gender, Age, Ethnicity, Socio/Economic, 40% Geographic/Demographic, Promotion, Prevention, Events and 32% Treatment, Rehabilitation, Facilities, Technology and Research are analysis in ‘Times of India’. The chart implies that two newspapers have more number of Promotions, Prevention, Events news and article when compared with the other categorization of news items.

III.III. III. FREQUENCY OF NEWS

Frequency of the news helps the researcher to understand how often the news items come on the newspaper. It shows how important the journalist gives to the elder’s health care.

Newspaper	Total number of news in a month	News covered on geriatric healthcare	Percentage
The New Indian Express	2490	28	1.05%
Times of India	3255	25	0.98%

Table 3. Frequency of news

The Table reveals that ‘The New Indian Express’ had more percentage of news covering geriatric health care compare to the other newspaper taken for the study.

III.III. IV. COLUMN- WISE COVERAGE

More the amount of news present in a newspaper more is the number of column it occupies. Generally the news given in four column news item is more than the news and article given in a single column news item and thus the importance given to certain issues can be measured using the parameter. The more the number of columns in a newspaper the more the importance is and vice versa.

Strength of the column	The New Indian Express		Times of India		Total
	In no%	In%	In no%	In%	
Single column	18	64%	20	80%	38
Double column	6	21%	2	8%	8
Three columns and Above	4	14%	3	12%	7
Total	28	100	25	100	53

Table 4. Column-wise coverage

The 'The New Indian Express ' had 64% of total news regarding geriatric health care in a single column while 'Time of India' had 80% of total news regarding geriatric health care respectively. 'The New Indian Express' When compared with two newspaper dailies had more number of single column stories about geriatric healthcare. 'The New Indian Express' had 21% of total news concerning geriatric healthcare in double column while 'Time of India' had 8% of total news about geriatric healthcare in double column. 'The New Indian Express 'had 14% of total news concerning geriatric healthcare in multi columns while 'Time of India' had 12% of total news about geriatric healthcare in three columns or more than three columns. The newspaper had a higher percentage of multi-column news stories involving older people than ' 'The New Indian Express' ' that were taken for the study.

III.III. V. PLACEMENT OF NEWS

The importance of news items can be judged through their placement. All the news items on the first page are considered as the most important news of the day. The news item on the second page is considered to be less important and it receives very less attention from the readers. Also feature kinds of news stories occupy the second page usually. Page 3 gets more attention from the readers than page 2 and hence stories featured in the third page are considered to be given more importance. National page varies from each newspaper and stories that have impact all over the country are featured in this page.

News Region	The New Indian Express		Times of India		Total
	In no%	In%	In no%	In%	
First page	Nil	0	Nil	0	Nil
Page 2	3	11%	2	8%	5
Page 3	9	32%	8	32%	17
National	Nil	0	2	8%	2
Others	16	57%	13	52%	29
Total	28	100	25	100	53

Table 5. Placement of news

Both the newspapers didn't carry any news concerning about geriatric health in the First throughout the study period. 11% of the news regarding geriatric healthcare in 'The New Indian Express' was found in the 2nd page of the newspaper. Similarly 8% of news in 'Times of India' was found in the 2nd page in the newspaper. 32% news regarding geriatric healthcare in 'The New Indian Express' was found in the 3rd page. Similarly 32% of news in 'Times of India' was found in the 3rd page in the newspaper. NO newspaper except 'Time of India' had featured stories about geriatric healthcare in the national page. It was presented on the national page of that paper. 57% of the news regarding geriatric healthcare in 'The New Indian Express' was found in the other page of the newspaper. Similarly 52% of news in 'Times of India' was found in the other page in newspapers that feature articles that are counted under the other page's category.

III.III. VI. PICTURES

A picture can convey a lot more information than a hundred words can. Nowadays printing technology is in peak form. Newspapers go for illustrations to present news in a pictorial way and to explain it clearly for the readers to understand it. Also illustrations are used to avoid vulgarity, violence, obscene and to prevent the identity of the source or victim.

Type of story	The New Indian Express		Times of India		Total
	In No	In%	In No	In%	
With Pictures / illustrations	10	36	15	60	25
Without pictures/ Illustrations	18	64	10	40	28
Total	28	100	25	100	53

Table 6. Portraying pictures/ Illustrations

'Times of India' had 60% of stories with pictures featured in it. 'The New Indian Express' had 36% of news with either pictures or illustrations respectively. 'The New Indian Express had 64% of stories without pictures featured in it. 'Times of India' had 40% of news without either pictures or illustrations respectively. Since the percentage is fair it is clear that newspapers showed interest and took effort to explain the stories regarding geriatrics healthcare of elders and to make it more effective.

III.III. VII. NATURE OF PICTURE SUPPLEMENTING THE ARTICLES

In case of reporting geriatric healthcare of elders, pictures of victims, Disease and Illustrations are featured to support the article. Sometimes file pictures are also used as supplements.

Type of story	The New Indian Express		Times of India		Total
	In No	In%	In No	In%	
Victim	5	18	4	16	9
Disease	6	21	4	16	10
Illustrations	7	25	6	24	13
File Pictures	10	36	11	44	21
Total	28	100	25	100	53

Table 7. Types of picture that are portrayed

Photos of victims and disease were found less than the illustrations are any other supporting materials. Newspaper opt file pictures for follow up stories and sometimes for features and file pictures are used more than any other supporting materials. 'Times of India' and 'The New Indian Express' carried illustrations to support the news about geriatrics healthcare of elders.

IV. CONCLUSION

The research dealt with the effectiveness of Health communication in the two newspapers The New Indian Express and The Times of India during the year of 2024. Content analysis was used to analyze health communication aspects of geriatric healthcare according to the statistical technique.

V. FINDINGS

- Hard news on geriatric healthcare is less (10%) compared to the follow up stories (8%) and feature (82%)
- Health tips (21%) is the major that is reported and Homecare occupies the second place.
- Government policy and therapy is the third most common topic and 'Times of India' cover news about geriatric
- Only 4 articles are reported on safety of geriatric over the study period.
- Most of the news on geriatric are single column news (64%) in 'The New Indian Express' and (80%) in the 'Times of India' this clearly implies that newspaper give less importance to geriatric healthcare.
- Though 'Times of India' has comparatively less number of articles (0.98%) on geriatric healthcare, it has comparatively more number of single column news
- More number of geriatric healthcare articles is seen in page 3 and supplementary pages of newspaper.
- No article is published in the first page among 53 articles.
- Photos and pictures are found more than illustrations or any other supporting materials.
- 'The New Indian Express' carries illustrations to support the news whereas other newspapers have it less.
- Newspapers don't have a separate beat for elderly people or for geriatric healthcare related issues. But they are trying to do justice as much as they can.
- Media go only for issues that come to limelight through the victims, community people or NGOs. They don't go in search of human aspects. They report only issues that have the capability of attracting reader's attention.

VI. SUGGESTIONS

Though there is a change in scenario in covering geriatric healthcare there are certain drawbacks like sensitivity, language to be used, etc. NO one objects to the role of the media in spreading awareness about elderly people or bringing out people to speak about it but they all expect more activity from the media.

- Multiplicity of voices should be used in reporting these issues to understand it from every perspective.

- Training and workshops are to be conducted to make journalists perceive and outlook issues in a geriatric healthcare view and in how to handle the elders.
- A journalist can be allocated for covering issues of elder healthcare by media organizations if they are not in a position to allocate a beat.

Media, which enjoys the pride of being the fourth pillar of the nation, has the responsibility in raising the status of elders in the country. Through educating people about geriatric healthcare and by giving extensive and justifying coverage to achieve. Justifying coverage here means both in terms of amount of coverage and the ways of reporting in which our media still lags behind.

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